

Study of mixed ligand complexes and kinetic parameters of [Zn-antibiotics-aspirin] system : a polarographic approach

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Stability constants and kinetic parameters of ternary complexes of Zn^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and aspirin as secondary ligand were determined at $pH\ 7.30 \pm 0.01$ and ionic strength of $1.0\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ ($NaClO_4$) at 25° using polarographic technique. Zn forms 1 : 1 : 1 [Zn-antibiotic-aspirin], 1 : 1 : 2 [Zn-antibiotic-(aspirin)₂] and 1 : 2 : 1 [Zn-(antibiotic)₂-aspirin] ternary complexes with these ligands. The nature of waves of Zn and its complexes were quasireversible.

A survey of literature reveals studies on antibiotics and aspirin compounds with different metal ions are in progress¹. The survey showed no work on complexation study of Zn^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and aspirin as secondary ligand polarographically, therefore, the present study was undertaken.

Results and discussion

Zn^{II} gave a well defined two-electron quasireversible reduction wave in $1.0\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ $NaClO_4$, pH range 7.10–8.50 at 25° , but $pH\ 7.30 \pm 0.01$ was selected on account of studying the complex formation in human blood pH . The values of $E_{1/2}^{quasireversible}$ of Zn^{II} was found to be $-1.010\ V$ vs SCE which by Gellings method¹¹ gave $E_{1/2}^{reversible} = -0.985\ V$. Similarly, $E_{1/2}^{reversible}$, from $E_{1/2}^{quasireversible}$ for complexes of Zn^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V, penicillin-G as primary ligands and aspirin as secondary ligand for different concentrations

of primary ligands (varied from 0.5 to 3.0 mM) and secondary ligand (varied from 0.05 to 0.20 M) were determined. In all these cases, irreversibility increases with increase of ligand concentration. Zn formed 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with aspirin and their stability constants are given in Table 1.

Ternary complexes were investigated at two fixed concentration of aspirin (0.025 and 0.050 M) by varying the concentrations of the antibiotics from 0.5 to 30 mM. Zn^{II} and its complexes gave the quasireversible waves. The overall stability constants (Table 1) of mixed ligand complex species were evaluated by Schaap and McMaster method² which indicated the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 [Zn-antibiotic-aspirin], 1 : 1 : 2 [Zn-antibiotic-(aspirin)₂] and 1 : 2 : 1 [Zn-(antibiotic)₂-aspirin] complexes.

The parameter (Z) which is a measure of degree of irreversibility is given by the following equation³,

$$Z = \text{antilog} [nF/2.303 RT (E_{1/2} - E)] + \log (i_d - i)/i.$$

The values of standard rate constant of Zn and its com-

Table 1. Stability constants of Zn^{II} -neomycin-aspirin system

$Zn^{II} = 0.5\ mM$, $\mu = 1.0\ M$ ($NaClO_4$), $pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01$, $temp. = 25^\circ$

Ligand	$\log \beta_{11}^a$	$\log \beta_{12}^a$	$\log \beta_{10}^b$	$\log \beta_{20}^b$	$\log \beta_{30}^b$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
Neomycin	—	—	3.60	6.51	9.101	4.80	7.65	10.00
Chlortetracycline	—	—	4.40	7.61	9.502	4.98	7.81	10.131
Oxytetracycline	—	—	4.50	7.81	9.860	—	7.98	10.25
Tetracycline	—	—	4.80	8.01	9.909	5.00	8.13	—
Penicillin-V	—	—	4.91	—	10.110	5.38	8.45	10.38
Penicillin-G	—	—	4.96	8.12	10.140	5.45	—	10.70
Aspirin	1.96	3.00	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aRef. 12. ^bRef. 4

plexes have been found to be of the order of $10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, which confirmed that the electrode processes are quasireversible. The charge transfer coefficients (α), regarded as the fraction of the applied potential, which either assist or hinder the process under consideration, also have the expected values⁴. The value of α (about 0.50) confirms that the transition state lies in the mid-point of dropping mercury electrode and mercury solution interface⁵. The values of standard rate constants (4.17×10^{-3} to $7.71 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) confirm that the reduction of electroactive species at the surface of the electrode is not fast.

The stability of mixed ligand complexes can be compared using relation⁶,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}]$$

The values of $\log K_m$ for [Zn-neomycin-aspirin], [Zn-chlortetracyclin-aspirin], [Zn-oxytetracyclin-aspirin], [Zn-tetracyclin-aspirin], [Zn-penicillin-V-aspirin] and [Zn-penicillin-G-aspirin] complexes were +0.045, -0.325, -5.405, -0.505, +3.880, -0.080, respectively. Negative values of $\log K_m$ show that the binary complexes are more stable than their ternary complexes, while the positive values show that the ternary complexes are more stable than their parent binary complexes⁵.

The sequence of stability constant of complexes with respect to the antibiotic ligands is neomycin < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < penicillin-V < penicillin-G. It is observed that Zn^{II} neomycin complex has the lowest stability among all the antibiotics. This may be due to the fact that a number of groups present in neomycin complex create steric hindrance. In case of chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline and tetracycline, the oxygen of first carbon atom and oxygen of amide group may take part in complexation with Zn^{II} . The order of stability constants of these tetracyclines is also in accordance with their pK values⁸. In the case of penicillin-V and penicillin-G the CO of the carboxylic group and ring nitrogen may take part in coordination with the metal ion⁹. Higher stability of the penicillin-G complex is possible than that of penicillin-V complex owing to the higher basic strength of the former ligand.

Experimental

Solutions of neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V, penicillin-G (Fluka) were prepared in double-distilled water. Aspirin was used as its sodium salt. The concentration of Zn^{II} in the test solutions

were 0.5 mM, and 1.0 M NaClO_4 was used to maintain the ionic strength as well as supporting electrolyte. The polarographic cell was connected with SCE via Latrine and Lingane cell¹⁰ in which a NaCl-agar-agar plug together with sintered disc were used and hence there was no possibility of precipitation¹¹ in the present studies. The pH of the test solutions was adjusted to 7.30 ± 0.01 . The C-V data for the test solutions were recorded after passing the pure hydrogen gas.

A manual polarograph with PL-50 polyflex galvanometer was used. The capillary characteristics were $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.02 cm (calculated) effective height of mercury. An Elico LI-120 pH meter fitted with glass and saturated calomel electrode was used. The temperature was maintained at 25°.

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